

Style for IRRN Contributors

Units of measure and styles vary from country to country. To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN)* request that contributors use the following style guidelines:

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).
- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g/pot) or grams per row (g/row).
- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.
- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha; not 60 kg/ha N.
- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the *IRRN*. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha.
- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg/ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.
- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage; Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.
- Type all contributions double-spaced. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Germplasm conservation

Observations on local rice germplasm in Liberia

S. S. Vjrmari, visiting scientist, Plant Breeding Department, International Rice Research Institute (formerly rice breeder, International Institute of Tropical Agriculture [IITA], Central Agricultural Experiment Station [CAES], Suakoko, Bong County, Republic of Liberia)

In 1977, 469 local rice varieties (mostly dryland), including 60 varieties of the African cultigen *Oryza glaberrima*, were collected by the Ministry of Agriculture, in collaboration with the Genetic Resources Unit of the IITA. These rices were maintained and evaluated at the CAES, Suakoko, in 1978–79.

The following observations were made on the materials:

1. Various agronomic characteristics that can be used in breeding programs such as height, tillering, growth duration, photoperiod sensitivity, and grain size and shape had high genetic variability. In the 1978 wet season, 209 single plants were selected for breeding in the progeny of those materials evaluated under dryland conditions.

2. The local varieties showed genetic variability. Variants and off-type plants were found among progeny of 74% of the single-panicle rows and 34% of the bulk rows. The variants included: dwarf to semidwarf plants among tall; photoperiod-insensitive (flowering) among photoperiod-sensitive (non-flowering) during the dry season under wetland conditions; purple culm bases among green culm bases; and typical to intermediate *glaberrima* types among *O. sativa*, and vice versa. These observations indicate that outcrossing as well as mechanical mixtures may occur in farmers' varietal populations. The presence of intermediate types of *O. sativa*-*O. glaberrima* indicates that *O. glaberrima* may provide such mechanisms.

Some dryland rice farmers reported that *O. glaberrima* plants continued to occur in their rice fields, despite attempts to rogue them.

Further studies are required to clearly identify the nature of genetic segregation and the role of *O. glaberrima* in providing an outcrossing mechanism in local dryland rice varieties. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Varietal resistance to rice diseases and insects in Liberia

S. S. Vjrmari, visiting scientist, Plant Breeding Department, International Rice Research Institute (formerly rice breeder, International Institute of Tropical Agriculture [IITA], Central Agricultural Experiment Station, Suakoko, Bong County, Liberia)

Liberia is in the tropical forest zone of high rainfall in West Africa and the country's ecological conditions are favorable for many rice diseases and insects. In conditions of subsistence

farming (shifting cultivation), the pests' severity is not usually apparent, but under permanent or intensive rice farming, the pests become obvious.

Rice diseases identified in Liberia include blast *Pyricularia oryzae*, leaf scald *Rhynchosporium oryzae*, brown spot *Helminthosporium oryzae*, sheath rot *Acrocyndrium oryzae*, sheath blight *Corticium sasakii*, sheath blotch *Pyrenochaeta oryzae*, glume discoloration (caused by various fungi), false smut *Ustilaginoidea virens*, udbatta *Ephelis oryzae*, and pale yellow mottle virus. The most serious are blast, leaf scald,

sheath rot, sheath blotch, glume discoloration, and brown spot. Pale yellow mottle virus may be serious in the future.

Rice insect pests identified in Liberia include caseworm *Nymphula depunctalis* (in wetland fields only); Diopsis *Diopsis thoracica*; stem borers *Maliarpha separatella*, *Chilo zacconius*, and *Sesamia calamistis*; whorl maggot *Hydrellia prosternalis*; leaf-feeding beetle *Epilachna*

sp; grain-sucking insects *Stenocorys* sp., *Aspavia* sp., and *Leptocoryza* sp.; and for stored grains, the common rice weevil *Sitophilus oryzae*. Observations on their incidence in various parts of Liberia indicate that the following can be serious in some situations: caseworm, stem borer, Diopsis, and grain-sucking insects.

The following varieties, which could be used in future breeding programs, have been identified as resistant to some of

the important pests: IR1416-131-5 and LAC 23 to blast; Tetep, IR4547-6-1-1, IR2035-290-2-1-1, and IAC1500 to leaf scald; Suakoko 8, IR2058-435-3-1, IR2071-105-2, IR2071-586-5-6, IR4422-6-2, and B462b-Pn-31-1 to brown spot; Brengut, BW78, BKN6323, and ROK 2 to caseworm; IR5, Suakoko 8, Gissi 27, LAC23, OS6, M55, 63-83, IR1754-F₅B-23, and IRAT 13 to the common rice weevil. ■

Yield losses caused by sheath rot

S. Srinivasan, assistant plant pathologist, Paddy Experiment Station, Aduthurai 612101, Tamil Nadu, India

A study was made of the yield losses caused by sheath rot damage on crops raised during the normal kharif in Thanjavur district, Tamil Nadu, where the disease has a maximum incidence of 65%.

In 1979 kharif, 100 diseased panicles were collected from the first tillers of hills in uniformly fertilized bulk plots of 10 rice cultivars. The grain yields from the panicles with different grades of

Yield losses caused by sheath rot disease, Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Grade 1 yield (g/sample)	Yield loss (%) at disease grade			
		3	5	7	9
ADT31	265.9	+0.5	13.2	48.1	81.6
IET2881	263.9	2.6	21.5	58.5	87.2
Pusa 4-1-11-1	202.2	+0.5	17.3	63.9	85.2
AD6380	272.1	8.1	40.4	65.0	89.5
AD5620	236.4	6.8	21.3	63.4	81.8
AD54-1	255.3	7.9	31.1	58.6	86.6
AS3827	277.8	4.2	20.9	55.7	83.6
CRM10-5747	228.3	3.5	21.2	61.5	85.2
Bhavani	308.9	2.7	16.1	58.0	80.8
IR20	262.0	7.4	35.7	65.3	89.8

sheath rot infection were recorded; the yield losses are shown in the table.

At disease grade 3, no yield loss was

observed in ADT31 and Pusa 4-1-11-1; in AD5620, IR20, AD54-1, and AD6380 the loss was 7--8%. ■

A greenhouse screening technique for ragged stunt resistance

H. Hibino, M. Roechan, H. Warsidi, and M. Muchsin, Indonesia-Japan Joint Food Crop Research Program, Central Research Institute for Agriculture (CRIA), Bogor, Indonesia, and Pests and Disease Division, CRIA, Bogor

Ragged stunt virus disease is transmitted by the brown planthopper (BPH) in a persistent manner. Climatic factors that affect the BPH population may also affect disease resistance scores in field screening. The disease symptoms are often unclear until the plant's heading stage in the field. Therefore, scientists need screening techniques that both eliminate the effect of climatic factors and allow detection of disease symptoms at the seedling stage.

In a project to develop such a screening technique for ragged stunt resistance, BPH originally collected at the Muara Experimental Farm, CRIA, were

Procedures for inoculating plants by means of viruliferous insects for ragged stunt screening. CRIA, Indonesia.

reared in a screen cage for 4 years. Ragged stunt virus, originally isolated from a diseased rice plant collected at Pandeglang, Java, in 1976, was maintained on the rice variety TNI or

Pelita I-1.

Twenty-five BPH females were allowed to lay eggs for 1 day on an infected plant covered with a plastic cylindrical cage. The eggs began to